

METHODOLOGICAL STUDY OF LEXICAL DERIVATIONS IN GERMAN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This article is about the methodological study of lexical derivations in German languages. In German languages word formation, morphemic structure and their teaching methods are discussed. The grammar, lexicology, and word formation of German languages have been studied from a historical perspective. Examples of word formation through lexical derivations are given.*

Keywords: *derivation, affix, inflectional language, analytic language, amorphous language, ablaut, lexical derivation, word formation, inflection, morphemics, affixation.*

Introduction

The question of the use of language in speech is of great importance at the present stage of development of linguistics, because this issue has long been on the agenda of our linguistic research. The main reason for this was that linguists have focused on the study of the complex system of language and its specific problems, and therefore the issues of interpretation of speech linguistics were of secondary importance. However, in the current era of linguistics, there is a need to study the use of language in speech, the role of the human factor and the cognitive-pragmatic problems associated with it. This, in turn, increases the prestige of the study of derivation patterns of language development. No serious monographic research has been conducted in Uzbek linguistics on the study of lexical derivation phenomena in German languages. In linguistic interpretations of the phenomenon of word formation, another phenomenon is distinguished by its study under the term derivation. The term was introduced to linguistics in the 60s of the last century by the Czech linguist E. Kurilovich. It should also be noted that most linguists interpret lexical derivation as synonymous with word formation. Lexical derivation requires word formation. Their basic principles are common.

At present, the issue of word formation is considered as an object of study in a number of branches of linguistics, including morphology, lexicology, dialectology, grammar. If we look at the science of linguistics, as well as the history of the development of German languages, the phenomena of word formation and those directly related to this process generally express a certain similarity in each language. But the cognitive meanings in word formation, the lexical, grammatical, and semantic features of artificial words, are radically different in each language. Therefore, there is still controversy about the phenomenon of word formation. While in most scientific works the phenomenon of word formation in languages is considered as an integral part of grammar, some scholars interpret word formation as a purely lexical phenomenon and consider it as an object of study of lexicology.

It should also be noted that a good knowledge of the internal laws of the methods and means of word formation also plays a worthy role in the study of a foreign language.

Of course, each branch of linguistics is inextricably linked. Also, most branches of linguistics are directly concerned with the study of word and word-formation phenomena.

According to Wikipedia, ancient German languages appeared about two thousand years and formed over the next millennium as the language of the people living in the area from the western part of the Baltic Sea to the southern sides of Mount Harz. 750, German languages spread around the coasts of the North Sea and the Baltic Sea, as well as on the island of Jutland and the southern parts of the Scandinavian Peninsula. The people who spoke this language occupied the right and left banks of the rivers Vistula, Elbe, Oder, Rhein. In the first and third centuries AD, the Germanic peoples spread to the east and south, approaching the Danube territories of the Roman Empire. [de.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/] The work of Cornele Tacitus, the mayor of Rome, entitled "Germany" contains information about the dialectal differences between the ancient German languages under the influence of internal phonological changes. [Cap. 43,1] The period that lasted from 3 to 7 centuries and was known in history as the "Great Migration of Peoples" and the socio-economic relations that emerged between people during this period, especially property relations The change paved the way for the emergence of a number of local languages belonging to the German languages. Thus, German languages began to differ from other Indo-European languages both phonetically and morphologically.

In the morphology of German languages, for example, there has been a shortening of consonants in the variation of noun cases. In particular, in the first millennium BC, the existing eight consonant forms in Indo-European languages were reduced to six in German languages. There was also a singular, binary, and plural form in nouns, and a rod category in nouns. In verbs, however, three tendencies — Indicative, Conjunctive, and Imperative — are formed relatively strongly, with two ratios — Active, Passive, and two tenses — Präsens and Präteritum in German.

Scholars point out that the following features played an important role in the separation of German languages from Indo-European languages as a separate group.

- In a system of strong verbs, internal inflections, especially the Ablaut phenomenon, developed;
- Weak verbs began to form their past tense form with dental additions;
- As a result of the inflection of the adjectives in the words following the demonstrative pronouns, the adjectives change first to the weak and strong, and then to the mixed variable suffixes.

It is known from history that after the death of Charles the Great, the leader of the great empire founded by the Franks, the empire was divided into three parts by Charles the Great's grandsons under the Treaty of Strasbourg, which came into force in 842 and the Treaty of Verdun in 843. As a result, German, French, and Italian began to be used as the state languages in the newly formed states. It was during this period that a union of Anglo-Saxon tribes from the German tribes occupied Great Britain, and the newly formed state was named England, and English was chosen as the official language of communication in the region.

In the development of the vocabulary of these states, founded by Germanic tribes, first of all, the daily activities and unique culture of the peoples who speak these languages play an important role. Lexical units of languages such as ancient Latin, ancient Greek, ancient Slavic, Celtic, and Finnish, which serve as ancestral languages in Indo-European languages, also play an important role in the expansion of lexical units in German languages. For example, French,

which was originally the language of the German Frankish tribe, was confused with Italian, Spanish, and Rhetoric in the Middle Ages, and became a language belonging to the Romance language group.

In turn, the western and northern German languages German, English, Icelandic, Danish and Scandinavian languages during the development of the three, the old, the middle and the construction of a new period of its lexical-morphological forms.

German languages are inflected languages. One of the peculiarities of inflected languages is internal inflections, that is, “the phenomenon of changing the vowel in the stem to another vowel - ablaut, the change of the vowel to another vowel with a similar pronunciation - umlaut and the formation of consonants in the word formation. New words are created based on changes that include characters such as 'change'. In analytical languages, however, suffixes play an important role in word formation. Nevertheless, under the influence of interlingual organic relations it is now possible to see the peculiarities of analytic languages in inflected languages, which in turn are characteristic of inflective, amorphous, and cohesive languages in analytic languages. For this reason, in modern German languages, such as English, German, and Swedish, affixation is used to form new words, compound words, from one word group to another. the role of new word-formation phenomena through transmission is incomparable. Due to the rapid development of cognitive linguistics in recent years, as in all languages, the cognitive properties of artificial words, as well as simple primitive words, require serious study. .

Nicolaus Janos Raag also noted that as the German language began to appear in written sources from the beginning of the Middle Ages, the need for not only derived words but also simpler, more artificial and compound words, especially compound nouns, increased in German. emphasizes. (S.89)

The first research work on the history of the development of Germanic languages, in particular the development of lexical units specific to Germanic languages, dates back to the 18th century. The work started by the Grimm brothers was continued in the 19th century by German scholars Friedrich Schlegel, German Paul, Ferdinand de Saussure, Franz Bopp, Rasmus Rask, V.G.Admoni, V.V.Shcherba. Research on German lexicology and German grammar intensified in the 20th century. In the 20th century, German scholars such as Werner Betz, Walter Hensen, and Johannes Erben began to study word formation in German from a historical perspective. By the 20th century, the emphasis on learning German was also increasing in the former Soviet Union. As a result, large scientific schools of the German language, the object of study across the country, began to emerge. For example, an F.A. from the University of St. Petersburg . Proof of our opinion is the emergence of such well-known German scientists as Brown, VM Zhirmunsky, V.P.Berkov, L.R.Zinder, T.V.Stroyeva, G.N.Eichbaum, K.A.Filippov, L.N.Grigoryeva, T.V.Ponamaryova, N.A.Golikova.

T.A.Katskova, who is currently conducting research at the University of St. Petersburg, wrote her ban article entitled “Pamyati Uchitelya T.V.Stroyevoy” (Sokolskoy)”. In addition to, L.R.Zinder and T.V.Stroyeva co-authored “Theoretical Phonetics and Theoretical Grammar of the German Language” and “History of the German Language”, “German Lexicology”, “Introduction to German Philology”, “German Dialectology” and “German Language”. He

published textbooks and manuals and organized lectures, special courses and seminars in these areas. [<https://nemphil.spbu.ru.lib> . Page 22]

It should be noted that in languages such as Old High German, Old English, Old Scandinavian, the lexical richness of the language increased, first on the basis of suffixes and then on the basis of suffixes and prefixes formed from prefixes.

In particular, word formation and word formation based on internal inflection and affixation are common in West German languages. Some research has also been done in this regard.

In particular, the Russian scientist Ye. A. Libert in his dissertation on 10.02.20 - Comparative-historical, typological and comparative linguistics "Typology of suffixed diminutive models in the West Germanic languages" in the candidate's dissertation In order to study, he compared the reduction suffixes in the West German languages [6:24]. In this study, the scientist first compared the diminutive suffixes in English, German, Dutch, Frisian, as well as plotdich and Yiddish, which are based on Old German. In his research, Ye.A. Libert noted that the suffixes in German appeared in the form "-kin", "-lin", and later these suffixes were used to describe the palatalization, assimilation and dissimilation of sounds in West Germanic languages. He used the relevant examples to show that the first and second shifts of consonants took different forms in different German languages, that is, these suffixes "-ke (n), -je (n), -t'e, -tsje, -çe (n) was able to show that it had arrived in appearance.

As a result of the drop of the "n" sound at the end of the word, this suffix appears in modern English as "-ie" or "-y". For example: Becky (a form of the name "Rebecca"), Cathie (a form of the name "Catherina"). Such suffixes are also found in modern English words such as "mummy - mother, daddy - father, pussy - kitten, bookie - booklet, buggie - stroller." It should be noted that a number of words in English are also formed with the suffix -ette, derived from the French. For example, Lisette - Lizahon, luncheonette - light food, and so on.

These diminutives have appeared in the Frisian and Dutch languages as "-ke, - (t) sje, -je and - (e) tsje, -pje, kje, respectively. For example, in the Frisian language: Jerske, Pieterke, kayke - key, nestke - nail; in Dutch: Annsje, Geartsje, Soukje, taffeltsje - board, stockje - stick, betje - bed and others. In Plotdich's language, the suffix is -the. For example, "bilt'e - photo". [6:13].

In modern German, on the other hand, we see that the monoftong vowels in the diminutive suffixes were replaced by diphthongs by the Middle and New Upper German period. Forexample: das Buch (book) - das Buchlein (booklet), der Tisch (table) - das Tischlein (table), der Bruder (brother) - der Bruderchen (littlebrother) and others.

Historically, lexical units of verbs and nouns were common in ancient Germans, while auxiliary word groups, especially prepositions, were less developed. It was not until the Middle Ages that most of the prefixes became prepositions as a result of the formation of nouns from artificial verbs. In Old Upper German, for example, a number of prefixes in compound verbs have become relevant words, prepositions, and forms not only in Osh form, but also in meaning. Such prefixes include: ana-, duruh-, for a-, furi-, fram-, gagen-, hinder-, in-, nidar-, ubar-, ûf-, umbi-, undar-, ûz-, wider- and others. [1:35]

Experiments show that fixed phrases in the German form "preposition + noun" are relatively rare expressions. There are many such phrases in English:

By day, at night, by car (by bus, by train, by ship, by boat, by plain ...), on foot, at home and so on.

In German, such derivations as "preposition + noun" are relatively rare:

NachJahr und Tag - within a specified period

In Bausch und Bogen - completely, completely

Von Mal zu Mal - every time

NachHause - home

ZuHause - at home

SchrittfürSchritt - step by step ...

We find that the similarity of the expressions in German and English in the form of "preposition and noun" is due to the fact that in German most of such expressions are formed by the direct connection of the preposition to the noun without the article. In which case we can come to the following conclusions.

We have witnessed that the term derivation also has its own history. In modern linguistics, Wilhelm von Humboldt distinguishes between internal and external form. After all, although each phenomenon in language is characterized by its own object of study, in fact, they require a whole organism, a system. As for the derivative nature of word-forming affixes, this functional sign is a sign that word-formers in the paradigm of affixal morphemes are functionally different from other affixes, lexical and grammatical form-formers. With the understanding of such a functional difference, two branches of linguistics called word formation and morphemics emerged.

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